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Solving fractional optimal control problems by a new Horadam-Galerkin method

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Abstract. In this study, we present a computational method for solving fractional optimal control problems (FOCPs). To solve this class of problems, we use Horadam polynomials and Galerkin method. These polynomials have four free parameters and this feature distinguishes them from other known classical polynomials. We construct a Riemann-Liouville integral operational matrix for the Horadam polynomials. Combining this matrix and the Galerkin method, the considered problem is converted to a system of algebraic equations. Also, the efficiency and accuracy of the proposed method is demonstrated by numerical examples.

1. Introduction

In this study, we focus on the following problem

$$\min \mathfrak{J} = \int_0^1 f(t, x(t), u(t)) dt, \quad (1)$$

subject to the following dynamic system

$$\begin{cases} D^\nu x(t) = g(t, x(t), u(t)), & t \in [0, 1] \\ x^{(i)}(0) = x_i, & i = 0, 1, \dots, [\nu] - 1, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where D^ν denotes the Caputo fractional derivative which is denoted in [3]. Recently, FOCPs have attracted significant attention due to their ability to describe dynamical systems. In this paper, we propose a new numerical scheme that is based on Horadam polynomials for solving a class of FOCPs. These polynomials depend on four free parameters a , b , p , and q through

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which by selecting these parameters various types of orthogonal and non-orthogonal polynomials can be constructed. Then, we introduce the Riemann-Liouville integral operational matrix of Horadam polynomials and we use the Galerkin method to design the proposed numerical method that affects the efficiency and accuracy of the method.

2. Preliminaries tools

2.1. Horadam polynomials

The Horadam polynomials represent a new generalization of sequences of second-order polynomials [2]. These polynomials, denoted as $H_m(t, a, b, p, q)$ or simply $H_m(t)$, are described by the recurrence relation

$$H_m(t) = ptH_{m-1}(t) + qH_{m-2}(t), \quad m \geq 2, \quad (3)$$

with initial conditions, $H_0(t) = a$, and $H_1(t) = bt$, where a, b, p , and q are real constants. By manipulating of these free parameters, various types of orthogonal and non-orthogonal polynomials can be constructed, such as the first and second kinds of Chebyshev polynomials, Pell polynomials, Lucas polynomials, and others as special cases. Moreover, in [3] is presented a new explicit formula for $H_m(t)$, in the following form

$$H_m(t) = \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor} \left[\binom{m-i}{i} (pt)^{m-2i} (q)^i \left(a + \left(\frac{b}{p} - a \right) \left(2 - \frac{m}{m-i} \right) \right) \right], \quad m \geq 1, \quad (4)$$

and, $H_0(t) = a$.

2.2. Function approximation

For an arbitrary function $f \in L^2[0, 1]$, it can be expressed using $H(t)$ as the following form

$$f(t) \simeq \sum_{i=0}^M c_i H_i(t) = C^T H(t), \quad (5)$$

where C and $H(t)$ are $(M + 1) \times 1$ vectors, given by $C = [c_0, c_1, \dots, c_M]^T$, and $H(t) = [H_0(t), H_1(t), \dots, H_M(t)]^T$. We obtain the coefficient vector C as follows

$$C = D^{-1} \langle f, H \rangle, \quad (6)$$

where

$$D = \langle H, H \rangle = \int_0^1 H(t)H(t)^T dt. \quad (7)$$

3. Riemann-Liouville integral operational matrix

In this section, we obtain the Riemann-Liouville integral operational matrix for Horadam polynomials. We consider

$$I^\nu H(t) \simeq P^\nu H(t), \quad (8)$$

where I^ν denotes the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral which is defined in [3] and P^ν is $(M+1) \times (M+1)$ the Riemann-Liouville integral operational matrix of order ν . For $i=0$, we achieve

$$I^\nu(H_0(t)) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} t^{\nu-1} * a, \quad (9)$$

that the operator $*$ is convolution product. We apply the Laplace transform in above equation, and gain

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{L}[I^\nu H_0(t)] &= \mathfrak{L}\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} t^{\nu-1}\right] \mathfrak{L}[a] \\ &= \frac{a(\nu-1)!}{\Gamma(\nu) s^{\nu+1}} = P_0(s). \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Taking the inverse Laplace transform of Eq. (10), the following relation is yielded

$$I^\nu(H_0(t)) = \tilde{P}_0(t) = \frac{a}{\nu\Gamma(\nu)} t^\nu. \quad (11)$$

By expanding $\tilde{P}_0(t)$ using terms of Horadam polynomials, we have

$$\tilde{P}_0(t) \simeq \sum_{j=0}^M c_{0j} H_j(t) = C_0^T H(t), \quad (12)$$

with

$$c_{0j} = D^{-1} \langle \tilde{P}_0, H_j \rangle. \quad (13)$$

We use the same process for $i=1, 2, \dots, M$, then we have

$$I^\nu(H_i(t)) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} t^{\nu-1} * \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor} \left[\binom{i-k}{k} (pt)^{(i-2k)} (q)^k \left(a + \left(\frac{b}{p} - a \right) \left(2 - \frac{i}{i-k} \right) \right) \right] \right). \quad (14)$$

To obtain $I^\nu H(t)$, we implement the Laplace transform in Eq. (14). Then, we have

$$\mathfrak{L}[I^\nu H_i(t)] = \mathfrak{L}\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} t^{\nu-1}\right] \mathfrak{L}\left[\sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor} \left[\binom{i-k}{k} (pt)^{(i-2k)} (q)^k \left(a + \left(\frac{b}{p} - a \right) \left(2 - \frac{i}{i-k} \right) \right) \right] \right] = P_i(s), \quad (15)$$

for $i=1, 2, \dots, M$. By using the inverse Laplace transform of Eq. (15), we derive

$$I^\nu H_i(t) = \tilde{P}_i(t), \quad (16)$$

Now, we can expand $\tilde{P}_i(t)$ utilizing Horadam polynomials as

$$\tilde{P}_i(t) \simeq \sum_{j=0}^M c_{ij} H_j(t) = C_i^T H(t), \quad (17)$$

with

$$c_{ij} = D^{-1} \langle \tilde{P}_i, H_j \rangle, \quad (18)$$

in which C_i for $i = 0, 1, \dots, M$ constitute the rows of P^ν .

4. Numerical method

In this section, we propose a numerical method for solving the considered problem (1) and (2). We use Horadam polynomials to extend $D^\nu x(t)$ and $u(t)$. We have

$$D^\nu x(t) \simeq X^T H(t), \quad (19)$$

and

$$u(t) \simeq U^T H(t), \quad (20)$$

that X and U are unknown vectors. By using properties of the I^ν in [3] and Eq.(8), we can write

$$x(t) \simeq I^\nu (X^T H(t)) + \sum_{i=0}^{[\nu]-1} x_i \frac{t^i}{i!} = X^T P^\nu H(t) + \sum_{i=0}^{[\nu]-1} x_i \frac{t^i}{i!}. \quad (21)$$

Also, we compute the integration (1), by using Eqs. (20) and (21) simply. On the other hand, due to the above discussion, Eq.(2) is converted to the following relation.

$$X^T H(t) \simeq g \left(t, X^T P^\nu H(t) + \sum_{i=0}^{[\nu]-1} x_i \frac{t^i}{i!}, U^T H(t) \right). \quad (22)$$

Suppose that

$$\Omega(t) := X^T H(t) - g \left(t, X^T P^\nu H(t) + \sum_{i=0}^{[\nu]-1} x_i \frac{t^i}{i!}, U^T H(t) \right). \quad (23)$$

by applying the Galerkin method in Eq. (23), the above relation transform to the following relation.

$$\tilde{\Omega} = \langle \Omega, H \rangle. \quad (24)$$

Then, we have, $\mathfrak{J}^* = \mathfrak{J} + \lambda \tilde{\Omega}$, where λ is the unknown Lagrange multiplier's vector. The following equations must be held in order to find the extremum of \mathfrak{J}^* .

$$\frac{\partial \mathfrak{J}^*}{\partial X} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \mathfrak{J}^*}{\partial U} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \mathfrak{J}^*}{\partial \lambda} = 0. \quad (25)$$

Finally, we use the "linsolve" package in Matlab to solve the algebraic system of equations. Moreover, we compute the approximate values of $x(t)$ and $u(t)$.

TABLE 1. The estimated values of \mathfrak{J} with $a = -1$, $b = -\frac{1}{2}$, $p = 1$ and $q = 2$ for Case 1 in Example 5.1.

Method	\mathfrak{J}
Chebyshev cardinal functions method ($n = 12$) [1]	0.192909
Fibonacci wavelet method ($k = 1, M = 4$) [5]	0.1929092715
Current method ($M = 3$)	0.1929092716
Current method ($M = 4$)	0.1929092981
Exact value	0.1929092981

5. Illustrative examples

Example 5.1. Consider the following FOCP

$$\min \quad \mathfrak{J} = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 [x^2(t) + u^2(t)] dt, \quad (26)$$

s.t.

$$D^\nu x(t) = g(t, x(t), u(t)), \quad 0 < \nu \leq 1,$$

$$x(0) = 1.$$

- **Case 1:**

The problem for $g(t, x(t), u(t)) = -x(t) + u(t)$ is to find the control $u(t)$, which minimize the quadratic performance index (26). For $\nu = 1$ the exact solutions of this problem is, $x(t) = \cosh(\sqrt{2}t) + \omega \sinh(\sqrt{2}t)$, and $u(t) = (1 + \sqrt{2}\omega) \cosh(\sqrt{2}t) + (\sqrt{2} + \omega) \sinh(\sqrt{2}t)$, where

$$\omega = -\frac{\cosh(\sqrt{2}) + \sqrt{2} \sinh(\sqrt{2})}{\sqrt{2} \cosh(\sqrt{2}) + \sinh(\sqrt{2})},$$

and $\mathfrak{J} = 0.1929092981$.

- The numerical values of the performance index \mathfrak{J} obtained by the proposed method with $\nu = 1$, $a = -1$, $b = -1/2$, $p = 1$, $q = 2$ and other numerical methods are reported in Table 1.
- Figure 1 displays the comparison of the exact and approximate solutions of $x(t)$ and $u(t)$ for $M = 3$, $a = b = p = 1$ and $q = -1$, and different values of ν .

- **Case 2:**

The problem (26) for $g(t, x(t), u(t)) = tx(t) + u(t)$ converts to time-varying problem. The Table 2 shows a comparison between the value of approximation solution for $M = 4$, $a = b = 1$, $p = q = -1$ with method in [4].

FIGURE 1. Approximation solutions of $x(t)$ and $u(t)$ for $M = 3$, $a = b = p = 1$ and $q = -1$ with different choices of ν for Case 1 in Example 5.1.

TABLE 2. A comparison of approximation of \mathfrak{J} for Case 2 in Example 5.1.

ν	Method in [4]	Our method
1	0.484268	0.4842677156
0.99	0.483463	0.4834626897
0.9	0.476024	0.4758829174
0.8	0.467669	0.4669784963
0.7	–	0.4580176677
0.6	–	0.4496034322
0.5	0.447038	0.4423989193

Example 5.2. Consider the following FOCP

$$\min \quad \mathfrak{J} = \int_0^1 \left[(x(t) - t^2)^2 + \left(u(t) + t^4 - \frac{2t^{2-\nu}}{\Gamma(3-\nu)} \right)^2 \right] dt, \quad (27)$$

s.t.

$$D_t^\nu x(t) = t^2 x(t) + u(t), \quad 1 < \nu \leq 2,$$

$$x(0) = x'(0) = 0.$$

TABLE 3. Comparison of the approximate values of \mathfrak{J} in Example 5.2.

Method	\mathfrak{J}
Genocchi polynomials method ($n = 9$) [6]	3.10951×10^{-7}
Current method ($M = 6$)	2.4469×10^{-7}
Current method ($M = 7$)	1.9166×10^{-7}
Exact value	0

For this example, the exact solutions of $x(t)$ and $u(t)$ with $\nu = 1.1$ are $x(t) = t^2$, $u(t) = -t^4 + \frac{2t^{2-\nu}}{\Gamma(3-\nu)}$ respectively and $\mathfrak{J} = 0$.

- The approximated values of the functional \mathfrak{J} , reported by the mentioned scheme, and the developed methods are compared in Table 3, for $\nu = 1.1$, $a = b = 2$ and $p = q = -1$.
- Figure 2 displays the behavior of absolute errors (AEs) for state and control variable with $\nu = 1.1$, $M = 5$, $a = -1$, $b = 1$, and $p = q = 2$.

FIGURE 2. The AEs of state and control variable for $\nu = 1.1$ and $M = 5$ with $a = -1$, $b = 1$ and $p = q = 2$ in Example 5.2.

6. Conclusion

Here, we proposed a numerical scheme to solve a class of FOCPs. To this aim, we constructed Riemann-Liouville integral operational matrix for Horadam polynomials and used these polynomials and the Galerkin method. The applicability of the scheme is demonstrated by illustrative examples.

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